

6b, R¹=CH₃), respectively in almost quantitative yields (Table 1). The compounds were characterised on the basis of m.m.p. with the authentic samples¹⁰⁻¹⁶ and further confirmed on the basis of their ir and

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF CHROMONES (2, 4, 6)*

Compd. no.	Yield %	M p.** °C
2a	94	59-60 ^a
2b	92	140-42 ^b
2c	92	73-74 ^c
2d	90	114-15 ^d
4a	94	102-03 ^e
4b	92	167-68 ^e
6a	92	124-25 ^f
6b	90	177-79 ^g

*The identity of the compounds was established on the basis of ir and ¹H nmr spectral characteristics; yields of chromones, from both the procedures, were almost the same and are based upon crystalline solid products with respect to chromanones taken.

**Lit. m.p. (°C): ^aRef. 10, ^bRef. 11, ^cRef. 12, ^dRef. 13, ^eRef. 14, ^fRef. 15, ^gRef. 16.

¹H nmr spectral data. A reasonable mechanism involves the initial formation of the intermediate 3-iodochromanone which in turn may undergo dehydroiodination to afford the corresponding chromone.

Experimental

The melting points were taken in open capillaries in sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Beckman spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz) instrument using CDCl₃ as solvent and TMS as an internal standard.

Oxidation of chromanones using DMSO-I₂-H₂SO₄. *General procedure:* To a solution of appropriate chromanone (10 mmol) in dimethyl sulphoxide (20 ml) were added a pinch of iodine and a drop of concentrated H₂SO₄. The solution was heated on a water-bath for 1 h, then cooled to room temperature and poured in ice-cold water with stirring. The gummy material so obtained, was extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (2×100 ml), washed with aqueous sodium thiosulphate solution (1 N; 2×100 ml) followed by water (2×100 ml) and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The solvent was then distilled off at reduced pressure and the resulting gummy mass was purified by passing through a column of silica gel G using hexane-ethyl acetate (9 : 1) as eluent (Table 1).

Oxidation of chromanones using DMSO-I₂. *General procedure:* To a solution of chromanone (5 mmol) in dimethyl sulphoxide (10 ml) was added a pinch of iodine. The solution after refluxing for 15 min, was worked up as above to yield the corresponding chromones (Table 1).

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